

RULE BOOK

ALTERNATIVE TRANSIENT PROGRAM

RB-19C.PDF

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XIX-C BCTRAN to derive [A], [R] or [R], [wL] of multi-phase transformer

Supporting routine BCTRAN can be used to derive a linear [A]-[R] or [R]-[wL] representation for single- or 3-phase (both core and shell type); 2-winding, 3-winding, or multiple-winding transformer; using test data of both the exciting test and the short-circuit test at the rated frequency.

Excitation losses can be taken into account by this model, although these losses can be neglected for both single-phase transformers and three-phase low-reluctance transformers. Some more explanation related to the zero-sequence excitation test for three-phase transformers seems to be desirable:

1. For three-phase transformers having one or more DELTA-connected windings, the core construction (shell or core type) is of minor importance. In such a case, the excitation test really becomes a short-circuit test because a closed DELTA acts as a short-circuit for zero-sequence currents.

It is therefore assumed that all DELTA connections are open during the zero sequence excitation test. In this case, the homopolar flux will close its path through the tank, where saturation effects will occur. Unfortunately, only one working point, rather than a complete saturation curve, can be specified currently. Because the excitation current can not be neglected, the excitation losses should be included.

On the other hand, if the DELTA winding remains closed, neither the value of the zero sequence exciting current nor the value of the zero sequence excitation loss is critical.

2. For three-phase transformers having only WYE-connected windings, the core construction is of major importance. A distinction should be made between low-reluctance and high-reluctance transformers.

a) Low reluctance: e.g. - banks of single-phase transformers

- Three-phase shell-type transformers
- three-phase, four- or five-leg transformers

In such cases, the homopolar flux closes its path over core-material, thus meeting a low-reluctance path. In this case, the zero sequence excitation current will be small, and the resulting excitation losses will be negligible.

b) High reluctance: e.g., 3-leg core type transformer.

The homopolar flux will close its path through the air and the tank (i.e., a high reluctance path). Because in such a case the zero-sequence excitation current is important, the resulting excitation losses can not be neglected. Even saturation effects will occur in the transformer tank. Unfortunately, only one working point, rather than a complete saturation curve, can be specified.

The short-circuit losses can, and always should, be taken into account.

Stray capacitances are ignored in this representation, which therefore is only valid up to a few kHz. As opposed to the XFORMER model, the BCTRAN model is even valid at low frequencies. This is due to the fact that the inductive and resistive parts of the short-circuit impedance are treated separately by this model. As a consequence, all off-diagonal resistive elements will remain zero, unless one takes into account the excitation losses. Since at DC these losses are zero, no non-zero resistive elements can occur at DC. Therefore, at DC conditions, no voltage can be induced from one winding into the other, which is physically correct.

Nonlinear behavior cannot be included in the BCTRAN model proper. Such behavior (saturation or hysteresis) can be taken into account, however, by adding type 93, 96 or 98 elements, connected to the proper transformer terminals (i.e., those windings which are closest to the core) in the electrical network, during the steady-state or transient run. In such case, however, it is mandatory to specify $I_{ex,dir} = 0$, since otherwise, the magnetizing inductance will be taken into account twice. Another possibility is to switch over to the "saturable transformer model" (section IV-E), which seems to work fine for all types of 2-winding transformers, but which can become unstable numerically for the 3-winding cases. The reason for this instability is not yet understood, but reordering the winding sequence might solve the problem.

Since this model uses the admittance formulation internally, the magnetizing current can have any value (even zero). On the other hand, of course, if the user specifies too little magnetizing current, the admittance matrix becomes nearly singular, so that the [R]-[ωL] output option becomes useless. Always use the [A]-[R] output option in such cases. Recall that [A] equals the inverse of [L]. Further, note that the floating-point miscellaneous data parameter EPSLIN (see Section II-B) is used as a singularity tolerance.

The punched card output of BCTRAN can immediately be used as input branch cards for mutually coupled, high-precision PI-circuit elements (high-precision TYPE 1, 2, ...) in the electrical network (Section IV-B). This is explained in section XIX-C-4. Assigning node names not only establishes the type of connection (WYE or DELTA), but also the phase shift (clock system) for a three-phase transformer (see example in section XIX-C-3).

Further, don't forget that all input data are only valid for the rated frequency at which all tests have been performed. Also note that it is impossible (even useless) to try to reset the value of this frequency!

The following subsection will explain the input data-deck structure for all possible BCTRAN cases. Next will follow a single-phase and a three-phase transformer example. In the last subsection, applications of BCTRAN output will follow. It should be stressed that all formulas to be used are in accordance with IEC Publication 76-1.

XIX-C-1 Input data-deck structure for BCTRAN

The most important differences between single-phase and 3-phase transformer input are the following:

- Single-phase transformers:
 - Leave all fields for the zero-sequence input parameters blank.
 - Use only the single-phase, positive-sequence power rating.
 - Set the flag NP = 1 on the excitation test data card (point 4).
 - Use the winding voltages, divided by $\sqrt{3}$ (point 5).
 - Assign only node names to BUS1 and BUS2 of phase 1 (point 5).
 - Leave flag ID blank on all short-circuit test data cards (point 6).
- Bank of 3 single-phase transformers:
 - Leave all fields for the zero-sequence parameters blank.
 - Use only the single-phase, positive-sequence power rating.
 - Set the flag NP = 1 on the excitation test data card (point 4).
 - For the winding voltage, the connection (WYE or DELTA) is important (point 5).
 - Assign node names to BUS1 and BUS2 for all three phases (point 5).
 - Leave flag ID blank on all short-circuit test data cards (point 6).
- Low-reluctance transformers:
 - The excitation behavior depends on the winding connection. If no DELTA-windings occur, the zero-sequence excitation current IEXZERO will be low, and the corresponding losses LEXZERO can be neglected. However, if a DELTA-winding occurs, it has to be opened during the zero-sequence excitation test. The excitation current, IEXZERO, will become important, and the corresponding losses, LEXZERO, have to be taken into account.
 - Values of the impedances (short-circuit impedance, magnetizing impedance) are equal in both the positive- and zero-sequence modes.
 - Set the flag NP = 0 on the excitation test data card (point 4).

- For the winding voltage, the connection (WYE or DELTA) is important (point 5).
- Assign node names to BUS1 and BUS2 for all three phases (point 5).
- Take care for flag ID (point 6).
- High-reluctance transformers:
 - In this case the zero-sequence excitation current will always be high, and hence, the corresponding losses should be taken into account. In addition, the excitation behavior depends on the winding connection, the same way as for the low-reluctance transformer.
 - The impedance values (short-circuit impedance, magnetizing impedance) are different in both the positive-sequence and zero-sequence modes.
 - Set the flag NP = 0 on the excitation test data card (point 4).
 - For the winding voltage, the connection (WYE or DELTA) is important (point 5).
 - Assign node names to BUS1 and BUS2 for all three phases (point 5).
 - Take care for flag ID (point 6).

The difference between 2-winding, 3-winding, or multi-winding transformer input is straightforward:

- NW, the number of windings per core leg, is an input parameter (point 5).
- Flag ID (point 6) is important for 3-phase, 3- or multi-winding transformers.

In general, an input data-deck for the BCTRAN supporting routine has the following structure:

1. BEGIN NEW DATA CASE.
2. BCTRAN -- special request
(Transfers control to the proper overlay.)
3. \$ERASE -- request (optional)
(Erase any card images that might exist in punch buffer.)
4. 1 excitation test data card
5. NW winding data cards
(NW = number of windings per core)
6. $NW \times (NW - 1) / 2$ Short-circuit test data cards
7. BLANK CARD terminating short-circuit test data
8. \$PUNCH -- request (optional)
(Flush contents of punch buffer of preceding BCTRAN case.)

Remark that the data of points 4 through 8 may be repeated as many times as desired. Each such grouping is a separate data case within the BCTRAN setup, corresponding to a different transformer.

9. BLANK CARD ending all BCTRAN cases
10. BEGIN NEW DATA CASE -- card to begin new EMTP data case
11. BLANK CARD ending all EMTP cases

For an example of such input, the reader is referred to benchmark DCNEW-8 or to sections XIX-C-2 and XIX-C-3. Let's discuss the different card formats in more extensive detail now.

Table XIX-C-1-1 Excitation Test Parameters	
	<p>Three phase: $IEXPOS = I_{ex} \times \frac{\sqrt{3}V_{LV}}{SPOS} \times 100$</p> <p>Where, I_{ex} = measured excitation current (nominal phase value) V_{LV} = rated line voltage on LV side (see card 5) SPOS = power base</p> <p>Note that if both IEXPOS = 0 and IEXZERO = 0, the [R]-[ωL] output request will generate an error message. Indeed, in such cases, the admittance matrix becomes singular, so it can not be inverted! In such a case, only the A-R option should be used. Note that $[A] = [L]^{-1}$.</p>
SPOS	The power base (in MVA), used for IEXPOS referencing.
LEXPOS	<p>Excitation loss (in kW) in the positive-sequence excitation test.</p> <p>Single phase: $LEXPOS = P_{ex,loss}$ (negligible). three phase: $LEXPOS = P_{ex,loss}$.</p> <p>Where, $P_{ex,loss}$ = measured excitation loss (nominal conditions).</p>
IEXZERO	<p>The exciting current (in percent) in the zero-sequence excitation test.</p> <p>NP = 1: IEXZERO = blank</p> <p>Three phase: $IEXZERO = \frac{1}{3} I_{ex,h} \times \frac{\sqrt{3}V_{LV}}{SZERO} \times 100$</p> <p>Where, $I_{ex,h}$ = measured excitation current (nominal conditions). V_{LV} = rated line voltage on LV side (see card 5). SZERO = power base.</p> <p>If at least one DELTA winding exists, it should be opened because for the zero-sequence current the closed DELTA would act as a short circuit path. For an open DELTA, the homopolar excitation current $I_{ex,h}$ always will be important. However, if the DELTA remains closed, neither IEXZERO nor LEXZERO are critical. Taking the positive sequence values is a good enough approximation then.</p>
	<p>If only WYE-connected windings occur, the homopolar excitation current $I_{ex,h}$ can only be neglected in case of a low-reluctance transformer, not in the case of a high-reluctance transformer. Typical values are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • three-leg core type: $IEXZERO = 100\%$ • five-leg core type: $IEXZERO = 4 \times IEXPOS$ <p>Note that, if both IEXPOS = 0 and IEXZERO = 0, the [R]-[ωL] output request will generate an error message. Indeed, in such cases the admittance matrix becomes singular, thus it cannot be inverted! In such case, only the A-R option should be used. Note that $[A] = [L]^{-1}$.</p>

SZERO	The power base (in MVA), used for IEXZERO referencing. NP = 1: SZERO = blank Three phase: SZERO = (non-zero) e.g. SPOS	
LEXZERO	Excitation loss (in kW) in the zero-sequence excitation test (nominal conditions). These losses can only be neglected for three-phase low-reluctance transformers, having only WYE-connected windings. Leave blank for both a single phase transformer and a bank of 3 single-phase transformers (NP = 1).	
NP	= 0 or blank	a true 3-phase transformer
	= 1	a bank of 3 single-phase transformers or one single-phase transformer
IT	= 1, 2, ..., NW: reference number of the winding from where the excitation test was made. Normally this is the low-voltage winding. Note that winding reference numbers are allocated in card type 5. Also note that, if both IT and IW are zero or BLANK, then the program connects magnetizing branches across ALL windings. Finally, if IT is specified, then IW also should be!	
IW	= 1, 2, ..., NW: reference number of the winding across which the magnetizing branch is to be placed. In most cases this will be the low-voltage winding, since this is the winding closest to the iron core.	
IP	Output request flag. = 0 or blank: matrices [A] and [R] requested as output. > 0: matrices [R] and [ωL] requested as output. < 0: both [A]-[R] and [R]-[ωL] requested as output. Don't forget to specify the \$PUNCH request (point 8)!	

5. Next come exactly NW data cards, one for each transformer winding. These cards can be read in arbitrary order, since each card bears its own winding reference number. The card format is displayed next:

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0
I	3		E	1	0	.	2			E	1	0	.	2						A	6		A	6		A	6		A	6		A	6		A	6																																																					
K			V	R	A	T				R									B	U	S	1		B	U	S	2		B	U	S	3		B	U	S	4																																																				
										(optional)									phase 1			phase 2				phase 3																																																															

Table XIX-C-1-2 Winding Parameters													
K	Winding reference number. This numbering should be <u>in order of decreasing (actually, non-increasing) voltage</u> , so that winding 1 is to be the highest voltage winding, winding 2 is the next highest, etc. The placement of the cards in the deck is in arbitrary order, though.												
VRAT	<p>Rated winding voltage (in kV).</p> <p>Single phase transformer:</p> $VRAT = V / \sqrt{3} \text{ (line-to-ground equivalent)}$ <p>Three-phase transformer or bank of 3 single-phase transformers:</p> <p>DELTA-connected: VRAT = V (line-line value).</p> <p>WYE-connected: VRAT = V / $\sqrt{3}$ (line-to-ground value).</p> <p>Note that V is the rated nominal line-line value to be used in all former and following per-unit calculations.</p>												
R	<p>Winding resistance (in Ohms, at rated frequency) of one phase.</p> <p>If the values differ in the three phases, the average value should be used.</p> <p>If the winding resistances are not known, their value can be derived automatically from the short-circuit losses Pij (see group 6), only if the following three conditions are fulfilled at the same time:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> NW ≤ 3 (see group 4). Pij > 0 for all short-circuit tests (see group 6). IL > 0 on FIRST short-circuit card (see group 6). 												
BUSi	<p>Node names of the terminals of the winding k in each one of the three phases. One pair of node names is needed per phase.</p> <p>If a terminal is connected to ground, then use a blank field for the name of that terminal.</p> <p>By assigning names to the winding terminals, the punched card output can be used directly for a subsequent transient simulation.</p> <p>Assigning node names not only establishes the type of connection (DELTA or WYE) but also the phase shift (clock system) for a three-phase transformer.</p> <p>Example:</p> <p>Dy5 500/230 kV</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="893 1669 1218 1869"> <thead> <tr> <th>BUS1</th> <th>BUS2</th> <th>PHASE</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>A1 C2</td> <td>C1 x</td> <td>R</td> </tr> <tr> <td>B1 A2</td> <td>A1 x</td> <td>S</td> </tr> <tr> <td>C1 B2</td> <td>B1 x</td> <td>T</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p>Fig.1 : Clock-system declaration.</p>	BUS1	BUS2	PHASE	A1 C2	C1 x	R	B1 A2	A1 x	S	C1 B2	B1 x	T
BUS1	BUS2	PHASE											
A1 C2	C1 x	R											
B1 A2	A1 x	S											
C1 B2	B1 x	T											

Table XIX-C-1-2 Winding Parameters

		Note that for a grounded WYE, x should be replaced by BLANK.						
			PHASE R		PHASE S		PHASE T	
K	VRAT	R	BUS1	BUS2	BUS1	BUS2	BUS1	BUS2
2	$\frac{230}{\sqrt{3}}$	-	C2	x	A2	x	B2	x
1	500	-	A1	C1	B1	A1	C1	B1
		Note that on the DELTA side a path to ground should exist, in order to avoid “floating subnetwork” warning messages. This problem is discussed in extensive detail in section IV-E-3.						

6. Next come exactly $NW \cdot (NW-1)/2$ cards, one card for each short-circuit test between a pair of windings. The cards can be read in arbitrary order, since each card bears its own pair of winding reference numbers. The card format is as follows:

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0
I2	I2	E 1 0 . 2			E 1 0 . 2			E 1 0 . 2			E 1 0 . 2			E 1 0 . 2			I2	I2																																																																																											
I	J	Pij			ZPOSij			SPOS			ZZEROij			SZERO			ID	IL																																																																																											

Table XIX-C-1-3 Short-Circuit Test Parameters

I, J	Reference numbers of the pair of windings between which the short-circuit test is made.
Pij	Short-circuit loss or load losses (in kW) in the positive-sequence test. Take care of the following: Single phase: $P_{ij} = P_{sh}$. Three phase: $P_{ij} = P_{sh}$. Where, P_{sh} = measured load loss (nominal conditions). Under certain conditions, the winding resistance, R (see preceding group 5 data), can be calculated from the load losses. See parameter R of the preceding group 5 for more details.
ZPOSij	Short-circuit impedance (in percent, at rated frequency) in the positive-sequence short-circuit test for winding “i” with winding “j” shorted. For single-phase: $ZPOS = \frac{U_{sh}}{I_{sh}} \times \frac{SPOS}{V_{HV}^2} \times 100$ 1.

Table XIX-C-1-3 Short-Circuit Test Parameters		
	<p>For three-phase: $ZPOS = \frac{U_{sh}}{\sqrt{3} I_{sh}} \times \frac{SPOS}{V_{HV}^2} \times 100.$ 2</p> <p>Where, I_{sh} = nominal current on HV side (line value).</p> <p>U_{sh} = measured short-circuit voltage on HV side (nominal conditions, line value).</p> <p>SPOS = power base.</p> <p>V_{HV} = rated line voltage on HV side (see card 5).</p>	
SPOS	Power base value (in MVA), used for ZPOSij referencing.	
ZZEROij	<p>Short-circuit impedance (in percent, at rated frequency) in the zero-sequence test for winding “i” with winding “j” shorted.</p> <p>For single-phase: ZZERO = blank.</p> <p>For three-phase: $ZZERO = \frac{U_{sh}}{I_{sh}} \times \frac{SZERO}{V_{HV}^2} \times 100 \times 3.$</p> <p>Where, I_{sh} = nominal current on HV side (line value).</p> <p>U_{sh} = measured short-circuit voltage on HV side (nominal conditions, line value).</p> <p>SZERO = power base.</p> <p>V_{HV} = rated line voltage of HV side (see card 5).</p> <p>Note: For a closed DELTA, the excitation test results with closed DELTA are almost the same as the short-circuit results.3</p>	
SZERO	<p>Power base value (in MVA), used for ZZEROij referencing.</p> <p>For single-phase: SZERO = blank.</p> <p>For three-phase: SZERO = non-zero value, e.g., SPOS.</p>	
ID	This variable is only important for three, or more, winding three-phase transformers.	
	= blank	In all single-phase transformer cases.
	= 0	<p>This is a flag indicating that the zero-sequence reactance will be calculated, using the zero-sequence short-circuit impedance and the resistance (automatically calculated) representing the positive-sequence short-circuit losses. Hence, the resistance of the group 5-data will NOT be used. This can be done in following situations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> In all two-winding three-phase transformer cases, regardless of the

Table XIX-C-1-3 Short-Circuit Test Parameters		
		<p>winding connection.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> For multi-winding three-phase transformers, where the zero-sequence short-circuit test only involves windings i and k. If during this test, an additional DELTA-connected winding (different from i or k) is involved, this DELTA must be open.
	> 0	<p>This is a flag indicating the fact that the winding resistances given on group 5-data will be used to obtain reactances from impedances for the zero-sequence test. Hence these winding resistances will represent the zero-sequence short-circuit losses. This situation can only occur as follows:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> For multi-winding three-phase transformers where the zero-sequence short-circuit test not only involves windings i and k, but also another winding (reference number = ID), typically closed-delta connected.
	<p>The following clarifies the rules for 3-winding transformers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Yyd-connection: "d" is the additional shorted winding in the zero-sequence test between "Y" and "y." YDd-connection: "d" is the additional shorted winding in the zero-sequence test between "Y" and "D." "D" is the additional shorted winding in the zero-sequence test between "Y" and "d". Furthermore, both these tests should produce identical impedances. Ddd-connection: The program cannot handle Ddd-connected windings without first opening the delta-connection. This agrees with field measurement experience: in order to be able to perform the zero-sequence test, the delta-connection should be opened anyway! 	
IL	Flag specifying how the winding resistance (group 5 data) should be obtained.	
	= 0 or blank	The read-in winding resistances (see group 5 input cards) will be used.
	> 0	The read-in winding resistance values of the group 5 data will be ignored. Instead, the winding resistance values will be calculated from the short-circuit losses "Pij", on condition that all restrictions mentioned above (see "R", point 5) are fulfilled.
	Note: This parameter should only be specified on the FIRST short-circuit test data card.	

7. A blank card comes next, to terminate the input of short-circuit test data.
8. Next comes the optional “\$PUNCH” card, a special-request card which serves to activate the LUNIT7 punching of branch cards:

Notes:

1. This optional card should be used whenever punched card output is desired.
2. This punched output will use the high-accuracy fixed-format notation for TYPE-1-2-3 elements.
3. We refer to section XIX-C-4 for rules to be followed when inserting the punched card output in an electrical network simulation.

Remark that the data of points 4 through 8 may be repeated as many times as desired. Each such grouping is a separate data case within the BCTRAN setup, corresponding to a different transformer.

9. To end all BCTRAN cases, a blank card should be entered next.
10. If the user wants to shut off the EMTP at this point, a “BEGIN NEW DATA CASE” card, followed by a blank card, should be entered next.

XIX-C-2 Single phase example

1. Data setup

Consider the case of a one-phase transformer with both primary and secondary windings grounded at one terminal node. The other terminals are called “P1” and “S1” for primary and secondary, respectively. Finally, the following data were obtained by measurements on this transformer at 50 Hz:

Power rating S	0.0063 MVA
Excitation losses $P_{ex,loss}$	65 W
Excitation current I_{ex}	1.85 Amps
Short-circuit losses $P_{sh,loss}$	95 W
Short-circuit current I_{sh}	16 Amps
Short-circuit voltage U_{sh}	8.3 Volts
Voltage rating V_{prim}/V_{sec}	220/377 Volts

The values for the actual input parameters will be derived hereafter:

A. For card type 4:

NW = 2 since we have a 2-winding transformer.

FREQ = 50 since both the excitation test and short-circuit test have been performed at 50 Hz.

IEXPOS = 6.4603 (%).

Indeed, the per-unit magnetizing current:

$$1.85 \times \frac{220}{6300} \times 100 = 6.4603\% .$$

SPOS = 0.0063 (MVA).

LEXPOS = 0.065 (kW).

NP = 1, because we have a single-phase transformer.

IT = 2, because the excitation test was made at the low-voltage winding, having reference number 2.

IW = 2, assuming the low voltage winding is closest to the core.

IP = -1, thus requesting all possible output. Note that IEXPOS = 6.4603%, hence no danger for near-singularity of the admittance matrix [A].

B. For card type 5:

A total of NW = 2 cards of this type will be used in this example.

Card K = 1 (HV-winding card).

- VRAT (1) = $0.377/\sqrt{3} \cdot 4 = 0.21766$ (kV) .
- The entry of R is not mandatory, since it can be calculated automatically by BCTRAN. If one would prefer to work manually, following formula must be used:

$$R(1) = 0.186 \text{ (Ohms)}.$$

Indeed, the short-circuit resistance:

$$R_{sh} = \frac{P_{sh,loss}}{I_{sh}^2} = \frac{95}{16^2} = 0.3711 \Omega .$$

Thus, the resistance of the HV winding (1) equals $0.3711/2 = 0.186$ Ohms.

- We further take BUS1 = H1 and BUS2 = blank (connection to ground).

Card K = 2 (LV-winding card).

- VRAT (2) = $0.220/\sqrt{3} \cdot 5 = 0.12702$ (kV).
- The entry of R is not mandatory, since it can be calculated automatically by BCTRAN. If one would prefer to work manually, following formula must be used:

$$R(2) = 0.063 \text{ (Ohms)}.$$

The short-circuit resistance $R_{sh} = 0.3711$ Ohms (see above) so the resistance of the LV winding (2) equals:

$$\frac{0.3711}{2} \times \left(\frac{220}{377}\right)^2 = 0.063 \Omega .$$

- BUS1 = L1 and BUS2 = blank (connection to ground).

C. For card type 6:

A total of NW * (NW-1)/2 = 1 card of this type will be used in this example.

I = 1.

J = 2.

P12 = 0.10363 (kW).

The short circuit test was performed using 16A rather than the nominal HV current I_{nom} . Hence the value for the short-circuit losses should be modified according to the following formula:

$$P_{sh,nom} = P_{sh,m} \times \left(\frac{I_{sh,nom}}{I_{sh,m}} \right)^2.$$

Where the index “nom” refers to nominal conditions and “m” refers to the actual measuring conditions.

Since $I_{sh,nom} = \frac{6300}{377} = 16.71 \text{ A}$,

we find $P_{sh,nom} = 0.095 \times \left(\frac{16.71}{16} \right)^2 = 0.10363 \text{ kW}$.

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ZPOS12 = 2.2994 (%).

$$ZPOS = \frac{8.3}{16} \times \frac{0.0063}{0.377^2} \times 100 = 2.2994.$$

SPOS = 0.0063 (MVA).

ID = blank because this is a single-phase transformer case.

IL = 1 because we want the program to calculate the winding resistances out of the short-circuit losses automatically.

The supporting routine BCTRAN will calculate the magnetizing shunt resistance (iron core loss). In order to verify the output, the user can check this parameter very easily:

$$R_{magn} = \frac{V_{LS}^2}{P_{ex,loss}} = \frac{220^2}{65} = 744.62 \Omega$$

Note that EMTP calculates a value R-self = 747.01 Ohms.

Input data cards for the BCTRAN processing of this case then could appear as follows:

```

BEGIN NEW DATA CASE
C -----
C      (input data correspond to excitation and short-circuit tests,
C      performed on 13/02/84 on a 1-phase transformer )
C
C Power rating: 0.0063 MVA
C Voltage rating: 220/377 Volts
C Excitation losses: 65 W
C Excitation current: 1,85 A
C Short circuit losses: 95 W
C Short circuit current: 16 A
C Short circuit voltage: 8.3 V
C -----
ACCESS MODULE BCTRAN
$ERASE
C -----
C Excitation data
C -----
C 3456789 123456789 123456789 123456789 123456789 123456789 123456789 123456789
  2 50.      6.4603    0.0063    0.065                    1 2 2-1
  1.21766                    H1
  2.12702                    L1
C -----
C Short circuit data
C -----
C 3456789 123456789 123456789 123456789 123456789 123456789 123456789 123456789
  1 2 .10363  2.2994    0.0063                    1
BLANK LINE ENDING SHORT-CIRCUIT TEST DATA

```

\$PUNCH
BLANK LINE ENDING bctran

2. Sample output

```
Comment card. NUMDCD = 1. | C data://B/TRAFO/BCTRAN1F.IN
Marker card preceding new EMTP data case. | BEGIN NEW DATA CASE
Comment card. NUMDCD = 3. | C -----
Comment card. NUMDCD = 4. | C (input data correspond to excitation and short-circuit tests,
Comment card. NUMDCD = 5. | C performed on 13/02/84 on a 1-phase transformer )
Comment card. NUMDCD = 6. | C
Comment card. NUMDCD = 7. | C Power rating: 0.0063 MVA
Comment card. NUMDCD = 8. | C Voltage rating: 220/377 Volts
Comment card. NUMDCD = 9. | C Excitation losses: 65 W
Comment card. NUMDCD = 10. | C Excitation current: 1,85 A
Comment card. NUMDCD = 11. | C Short circuit losses: 95 W
Comment card. NUMDCD = 12. | C Short circuit current: 16 A
Comment card. NUMDCD = 13. | C Short circuit voltage: 8.3 V
Comment card. NUMDCD = 14. | C -----
Generate transformer [R],[L] or [A],[R]. | ACCESS MODULE BCTRAN
Erase all of 0 cards in the punch buffer. | $ERASE
Comment card. NUMDCD = 17. | C -----
Comment card. NUMDCD = 18. | C Excitation data
Comment card. NUMDCD = 19. | C -----
Comment card. NUMDCD = 20. | C 3456789 123456789 123456789 123456789 123456789 123456789 123456789 123456789
Excit. card. 2 5.00E+01 6.46E+00 6.30E-03 | 2 50. 6.4603 0.0063 0.065 1 2 2-1
Winding card. 1 2.18E-01 0.00E+00 "H1" | 1.21766 H1
Winding card. 2 1.27E-01 0.00E+00 "L1" | 2.12702 L1

Excitation test made from winding number 2. Magnetizing impedance is placed across winding number 2.
Positive sequence Zero sequence Closed delta
From To Load loss [kW] Impedance [percent] Rating [MVA] Impedance [percent] Rating [MVA] in
Comment card. NUMDCD = 24. | C -----
Comment card. NUMDCD = 25. | C Short circuit data
Comment card. NUMDCD = 26. | C -----
Comment card. NUMDCD = 27. | C 3456789 123456789 123456789 123456789 123456789 123456789 123456789 123456789
Short test. 1 2 1.04E-01 2.30E+00 | 1 2 .10363 2.2994 0.0063 2.29940 0.006 0 1
1 2 0.10363 2.29940 | 0.006 2.29940 0.006 0
Short test. 0 0 0.00E+00 0.00E+00 | BLANK LINE ENDING SHORT-CIRCUIT TEST DATA
ILOSS = 1
Resistance matrix values calculated from load losses.
Shunt resistances for representation of excitation losses.
Place the shunt resistance matrix across winding 2 with R-self [ohm] = 7.47008966E+02 and R-mutual [ohm] = 0.00000000E+00

Branch cards with [A], [R] in wide ($VINTAGE, 1), fixed format are created next. Use a $PUNCH data card to see a copy of these
on LUNIT6. Matrix [A] is the inverse inductance matrix in [1/henries], whereas [R] is resistance matrix in [ohms].

Branch cards with [R], [wL] in wide ($VINTAGE, 1), fixed format are created next. Use a $PUNCH data card to see a copy of these
on LUNIT6. Radian frequency w corresponds to the input frequency FREQ = 5.00000000E+01 Hz.
Request for flushing of punch buffer. |$PUNCH

A listing of 80-column card images now being flushed from punch buffer follows.
=====
123456789012345678901234567890123456789012345678901234567890123456789012345678901234567890123456789
=====
C <++++> Cards punched by support routine on 07-Feb-91 09.44.22 <++++>
C ACCESS MODULE BCTRAN
C $ERASE
C C -----
C C Excitation data
C C -----
C C 3456789 123456789 123456789 123456789 123456789 123456789 123456789 123456789
C 2 50. 6.4603 0.0063 0.065 1 2 2
C 1.21766 H1
C 2.12702 L1
C C -----
C C Short circuit data
C C -----
C C 3456789 123456789 123456789 123456789 123456789 123456789 123456789 123456789
C 1 2 .10363 2.2994 0.0063 1
C BLANK LINE ENDING SHORT-CIRCUIT TEST DATA
$VINTAGE, 1,
1L1 747.00896590667
USE AR
1H1 866.71803330735 .18554656040922
2L1 -1485.197977718 0.0
2547.6262427514 .06318876613197
$VINTAGE, 0,
$UNITS, -1.,-1.
USE RL
C ----- << case separator >> -----
$VINTAGE, 1,
1L1 747.00896590667
USE AR
1 866.71803330735 .18554656040922
2 -1485.197977718 0.0
2547.6262427514 .06318876613197
$VINTAGE, 0,
$UNITS, -1.,-1.
USE RL
C ----- << case separator >> -----
$VINTAGE, 1,
```

```

LL1                747.00896590667
USE AR
1                  866.71803330735 .18554656040922
2                  -1485.197977718   0.0
                  2547.6262427514 .06318876613197
$VINTAGE, 0,
$UNITS, -1.,-1.
USE RL
C ----- << case separator >> -----
$VINTAGE, 1,
LL1                747.00896590667
USE RL
$UNITS, 0.50E+02 , 0.
1H1                .18554656040922  354.0518885064
2L1                0.0 206.40278389066
                  .06318876613197 120.45061844065
$VINTAGE, 0,
$UNITS, -1.,-1.
USE RL
C ----- << case separator >> -----
$VINTAGE, 1,
LL1                747.00896590667
USE RL
$UNITS, 0.50E+02 , 0.
1                  .18554656040922  354.0518885064
2                  0.0 206.40278389066
                  .06318876613197 120.45061844065
$VINTAGE, 0,
$UNITS, -1.,-1.
USE RL
C ----- << case separator >> -----
$VINTAGE, 1,
LL1                747.00896590667
USE RL
$UNITS, 0.50E+02 , 0.
1                  .18554656040922  354.0518885064
2                  0.0 206.40278389066
                  .06318876613197 120.45061844065
$VINTAGE, 0,
$UNITS, -1.,-1.
USE RL
C ----- << case separator >> -----
===== < End of LUNIT7 punched cards as flushed by $PUNCH request > =====

```

Note:

1. The shunt resistances representing the excitation losses across winding 2 are added automatically.
2. The "\$UNITS, -1., -1." request is used to toggle back to the normal XOPT and COPT values used further in the network.

XIX-C-3 Three-phase example

1. Data setup

Consider the case of a three-legged core-type, three-phase transformer with both primary and secondary windings WYE-connected, and with both STAR-points grounded (YNyn0). The other terminals are called BUS1_R, BUS1_S, BUS1_T and BUS2_R, BUS2_S, BUS2_T respectively. Further, following data were obtained by standard measurements on this transformer (at 50 Hz):

Power rating S	35.0 MVA
Voltage rating	132.0 / 11.05 kV
Direct measurements:	
Excitation losses	18.112 kW
Excitation current	2.39 A
Excitation voltage	11.01 kV
Short-circuit losses	192.53 kW
Short-circuit current	153.1 A

Short-circuit voltage	35.213 kV
Homopolar measurements:	
Excitation losses	115.325 kW
Excitation current	500.0 A
Excitation voltage	1.183 kV
Short-circuit losses	8.825 kW
Short-circuit current	70. A
Short-circuit voltage	2.86 kV

The values for the actual input parameters are derived hereafter:

A. For card type 4:

NW = 2 since, again, we have a 2-winding transformer.

FREQ = 50.0 (Hz).

Indeed all tests have been performed at 50 Hz.

IEXPOS = 0.1316 (%).

Because the direct excitation test was not performed under nominal conditions, a current upgrading must be performed:

$$I_o = 2.39 \times \frac{11.05}{11.01} = 2.4074 \text{ A} .$$

Converting this value to percent values results in:

$$\text{IEXPOS} = 2.4074 \times 10^{-3} \times \frac{\sqrt{3} \times 11.05}{35} \times 100 = 0.1316\% .$$

SPOS = 35.0 (MVA).

LEXPOS = 18.244 (kW).

Because the direct excitation test was not performed under nominal conditions, an upgrading of the losses must be performed:

$$\text{LEXPOS} = 18.112 \times \left(\frac{11.05}{11.01} \right)^2 = 18.244 \text{ kW} .$$

IEXZERO = 49.15 (%).

Because the homopolar excitation test was not performed under nominal conditions, again a current upgrading must be performed:

$$I_o = \frac{500}{3} \times \frac{11.05}{\sqrt{3} \times 1.183} = 898.81 \text{ A} .$$

In percent values this results in:

$$\text{IEXZERO} = 898.81 \times 10^{-3} \times \frac{\sqrt{3} \times 11.05}{35} \times 100 = 49.15\%$$

Note that this is only half of the “Rule of Thumb” value from Table XIX-C-1-1.

SZERO = 35.0 (MVA).

LEXZERO = 3353.93 (kW).

Upgrading to nominal conditions is necessary for the homopolar excitation losses too:

$$\text{LEXZERO} = 115.325 \times \left(\frac{11.05}{\sqrt{3} \times 1.183} \right)^2 = 3353.93 \text{ kW}$$

NP = 0, a true three-phase transformer.

IT = 2, excitation tests were made from the low-voltage side (2).

IW = 2, the magnetizing branch should be placed across the low-voltage winding (2).

IP = -1, we request both [A]-[R] and [R]-[ωL] output.

B. For card type 5:

A total of NW = 2 cards of this type will be used in this example.

Card k = 1 (HV-winding).

VRAT = 76.21 (kV); line-to-ground value, because the winding is WYE-connected ($132.0/\sqrt{3}$ 8).

The entry for R is not mandatory, but it can be derived easily:

$$R_{s,h} = \frac{1}{3} \times \left(\frac{192530.0}{153.1^2} \right) = 2.738 \Omega$$

$$\text{hence, } R_1 = \frac{1}{2} R_{s,h} = 1.369 \Omega$$

Card k = 2 (LV-winding)

VRAT = 6.38 (kV); line-to-ground value, because the winding is WYE-connected ($11.05/\sqrt{3}$ 9).

The entry for R is not mandatory, but it can be derived easily:

$$R_s = \frac{1}{3} (R_{mh} + 2R_{md}) = 4474 \Omega$$

The allocation of names to the winding terminals is as follows:

Fig.2: Clock-system declaration

C. For card type 6:

A total of $NW \times (NW-1)/2 = 1$ card of this type is needed in this example:

I = 1.

J = 2.

P12 = 192.53 (kW).

The direct short-circuit test was performed under nominal conditions.

ZPOS12 = 26.691 (%).

$$ZPOS12 = \frac{35.213}{0.153} \times \frac{35/\sqrt{3}}{132^2} \times 100 = 26.691\%$$

The test was performed under nominal conditions.

SPOS = 35. (MVA).

ZZERO12 = 24.6213 (%).

$$ZZERO12 = 3 \times \frac{2860}{70} \times \frac{35}{132^2} \times 100 = 24.6213\%$$

SZERO = 35. (MVA).

ID= 0; zero-sequence reactance can be calculated automatically (using positive sequence load losses or short-circuit losses), because this is a two-winding transformer.

IL = 1; the winding resistance can be calculated automatically (using positive-sequence short-circuit losses), because this is a two-winding transformer and all short-circuit values are positive.

Input data cards for the BCTTRAN processing of this case then could appear as follows:

```
BEGIN NEW DATA CASE
ACCESS MODULE BCTTRAN
$ERASE
C |   FREQ|   IEXPOS|   SPOS|   LEXPOS|   IEXZERO|   SZERO|   LEXZERONPITIWIP
  2   50.   .1311   35.   18.244   49.15   35.   3353.93  0 2 2-1
C k|   VRAT|   R1| |bus1| |bus2| |bus1| |bus2| |bus1| |bus2|
  1   76.21   BUS1_RBUSH  BUS1_SBUSH  BUS1_TBUSH
C k|   VRAT|   R2| |bus1| |bus2| |bus1| |bus2| |bus1| |bus2|
  2    6.38   BUS2_RBUSL  BUS2_SBUSL  BUS2_TBUSL
C | |   PIJ|   ZPOSIJ|   SPOS|   ZZEROIJ|   SHOMIDIL
  1 2   192.53   26.691   35.   24.6213   35. 0 1
BLANK CARD TERMINATE INPUT OF SHORT-CIRCUIT TEST DATA
$PUNCH
BLANK
BEGIN NEW DATA CASE
```

2. Sample output

```
Comment card.  NUMDCD = 1.
Marker card preceding new EMTP data case.
Comment card.  NUMDCD = 3.
Comment card.  NUMDCD = 4.
Comment card.  NUMDCD = 5.
Comment card.  NUMDCD = 6.
Comment card.  NUMDCD = 7.
Comment card.  NUMDCD = 8.
Comment card.  NUMDCD = 9.
Comment card.  NUMDCD = 10.
Comment card.  NUMDCD = 11.
Comment card.  NUMDCD = 12.
Comment card.  NUMDCD = 13.
Comment card.  NUMDCD = 14.
Comment card.  NUMDCD = 15.
Comment card.  NUMDCD = 16.
Comment card.  NUMDCD = 17.
|C data://B/TRAFO/BCTTRAN3F.IN
|BEGIN NEW DATA CASE
|C power rating: 35. MVA
|C Voltage rating: 132./11.05 kV
|C direct measurements:
|C Excitation losses      : 18.112 kW
|C Excitation current    : 2.39 A
|C Excitation voltage    : 11.01 kV
|C short-circuit losses  : 192.53 kW
|C short-circuit current : 153.1 A
|C short-circuit voltage : 35.213 kV
|C homopolar measurements:
|C Excitation losses      : 115.325 kW
|C excitation current    : 500. A
|C excitation voltage    : 1.183 kV
|C short-circuit losses  : 8.825 kW
|C short-circuit current : 70. A
```

```

Comment card. NUMDCD = 18. |C short-circuit voltage : 2.86 kV
Generate transformer [R],[L] or [A],[R]. |ACCESS MODULE BCTRAN
Erase all of 0 cards in the punch buffer. |$ERASE
Comment card. NUMDCD = 21. |C | FREQ| IEXPOS| SPOS| LEXPOS| IEXZERO| SZERO| LEXZERONPITIWI
Excit. card. 2 5.00E+01 1.31E-01 3.50E+01 | 2 50. .1311 35. 18.244 49.15 35. 3353.93 0 2 2-1
Comment card. NUMDCD = 23. |C k| VRAT| R1| |bus1| |bus2| |bus1| |bus2| |bus1| |bus2|
Winding card. 1 7.62E+01 0.00E+00 "BUS1_R". | 1 76.21 | | | | | | | | | |
Comment card. NUMDCD = 25. |C k| VRAT| R2| |bus1| |bus2| |bus1| |bus2| |bus1| |bus2|
Winding card. 2 6.38E+00 0.00E+00 "BUS2_R". | 2 6.38 | | | | | | | | | |

```

Excitation test made from winding number 2. Magnetizing impedance is placed across winding number 2.

From	To	Load loss [kW]	Impedance [percent]	Rating [MVA]	Impedance [percent]	Rating [MVA]	in
Positive sequence							
Zero sequence							
Closed delta							
Comment card.	NUMDCD = 27.						
Short test.	1 2	1.93E+02	2.67E+01	1 2	192.53	26.691	35. 24.6213 35. 0 1
	1 2	192.53000	26.69100		35.000	24.62130	35.000 0
Short test.	0 0	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	BLANK CARD TERMINATE INPUT OF SHORT-CIRCUIT TEST DATA			

ILOSS = 1
Resistance matrix values calculated from load losses.

Shunt resistances for representation of excitation losses.

Place the shunt resistance matrix across winding 2 with R-self [ohm] = 4.47446552E+03 and R-mutual [ohm] = -2.21891079E+03

Branch cards with [A], [R] in wide (\$VINTAGE, 1), fixed format are created next. Use a \$PUNCH data card to see a copy of these on LUNIT6. Matrix [A] is the inverse inductance matrix in [1/henries], whereas [R] is resistance matrix in [ohms].

Branch cards with [R], [wL] in wide (\$VINTAGE, 1), fixed format are created next. Use a \$PUNCH data card to see a copy of these on LUNIT6. Radian frequency w corresponds to the input frequency FREQ = 5.00000000E+01 Hz.
Request for flushing of punch buffer. |\$PUNCH

A listing of 80-column card images now being flushed from punch buffer follows.

```

=====
123456789012345678901234567890123456789012345678901234567890123456789012345678901234567890123456789
=====
C <++++> Cards punched by support routine on 07-Feb-91 09.49.30 <++++>
C ACCESS MODULE BCTRAN
C $ERASE
C C | FREQ| IEXPOS| SPOS| LEXPOS| IEXZERO| SZERO| LEXZERONPITIWI
C 2 50. .1311 35. 18.244 49.15 35. 3353.93 0 2 2
C C k| VRAT| R1| |bus1| |bus2| |bus1| |bus2| |bus1| |bus2|
C 1 76.21 | | | | | | | | | |
C C k| VRAT| R2| |bus1| |bus2| |bus1| |bus2| |bus1| |bus2|
C 2 6.38 | | | | | | | | | |
C C | | PIJ| ZPOSIJ| SPOS| ZZEROIJ| SHOMIDIL
C 1 2 192.53 26.691 35. 24.6213 35. 0 1
C BLANK CARD TERMINATE INPUT OF SHORT-CIRCUIT TEST DATA
$VINTAGE, 1,
1BUS2_RBUSL 4474.4655159359
2BUS2_SBUSL -2218.910788382
4474.4655159359
3BUS2_TBUSL -2218.910788382
-2218.910788382
4474.4655159359
USE AR
1BUS1_RBUSH 2.4311266503345 1.369233463069
2BUS2_RBUSL -29.04015078715 0.0
361.43763967638 .0095961038351
3BUS1_SBUSL .06629545237001 0.0
-.7919085305828 0.0
2.4311266503345 1.369233463069
4BUS2_SBUSL -.7919085305828 0.0
23.900085059572 0.0
-29.04015078715 0.0
361.43763967638 .0095961038351
5BUS1_TBUSL .06629545237001 0.0
-.7919085305828 0.0
.06629545237001 0.0
-.7919085305828 0.0
2.4311266503345 1.369233463069
6BUS2_TBUSL -.7919085305828 0.0
23.900085059572 0.0
-.7919085305828 0.0
23.900085059572 0.0
-29.04015078715 0.0
361.43763967638 .0095961038351
$VINTAGE, 0,
$UNITS, -1.,-1.
USE RL
C ----- << case separator >> -----
$VINTAGE, 1,
1BUS2_RBUSL 4474.4655159359
2BUS2_SBUSL -2218.910788382
4474.4655159359
3BUS2_TBUSL -2218.910788382
-2218.910788382
4474.4655159359
USE RL
$UNITS, 0.50E+02, 0.
1BUS1_RBUSH 1.369233463069 276371.46702425
2BUS2_RBUSL 0.0 23125.893148548
.0095961038351 1936.0083753803
3BUS1_SBUSL 0.0 -137608.3908058
0.0 -11519.74302843
1.369233463069 276371.46702425
4BUS2_SBUSL 0.0 -11519.74302843
0.0 -964.3873575831

```

```

0.0 23125.893148548
.0095961038351 1936.0083753803
5BUS1_TBUSH 0.0 -137608.3908058
0.0 -11519.74302843
0.0 -137608.3908058
0.0 -11519.74302843
1.369233463069 276371.46702425
6BUS2_TBUSL 0.0 -11519.74302843
0.0 -964.3873575831
0.0 -11519.74302843
0.0 -964.3873575831
0.0 23125.893148548
.0095961038351 1936.0083753803
$VINTAGE, 0,
$UNITS, -1.,-1.
USE RL
C ----- << case separator >> -----
=====< End of LUNIT7 punched cards as flushed by $PUNCH request >=====

```

Note:

1. Observe the mutually coupled shunt resistances representing the excitation losses across winding 2. Although these values are calculated by EMTP, results can be verified easily:

$$\text{Direct: } R_{m,d} = \frac{11010^2}{18112} = 6693 \Omega . \quad 10$$

$$\text{Homopolar: } R_{m,h} = 3 \times \frac{1183^2}{115325} = 36.41 \Omega 11.$$

Then it follows:

$$R_s = \frac{1}{3}(R_{m,h} + 2 R_{m,d}) = 4474 \Omega , \text{ and} \quad 12$$

$$R_m = \frac{1}{3}(R_{m,h} - R_{m,d}) = -2219 \Omega \quad 13.$$

2. In this example, the homopolar short-circuit losses can not be covered only by winding resistance losses. Hence additional losses can be confined to a single resistance, to be placed between BUSH (star point of HV-side) and ground. The value of this resistance is calculated as follows:

$$P_{sh,hom} = 8.825 \times \left(\frac{153.09}{70/3} \right)^2 = 379.94 \text{ kW} \quad 14.$$

Indeed, we had to upgrade the losses, since the homopolar short circuit test was not performed under nominal conditions.

$$P_{sh,extra} = P_{sh,hom} - P_{sh,dir} \quad (\text{both under nominal conditions}), \text{ or}$$

$$= 379.94 - 192.53 = 187.41 \text{ kW} .$$

$$R_{sh,extra} = \frac{187410}{(3 \times 153.09)^2} = 0.889 \Omega 15$$

3. The "\$UNITS, -1., -1." request is used to toggle back to the normal XOPT and COPT values used further in the network.

XIX-C-4 Applications of BCTRAN Output

TYPE-1-2-3 punched output can be used as branch cards immediately, thus representing the transformer. This is explained in more detail in Section IV-B. In addition, one should obey the following rules when inserting the punched card output in an electrical network simulation:

1. [A]-[R] option: value of XOPT has no effect

```
$VINTAGE, 1
  USE AR
C punched output cards: A in Henry-1, R in Ohms and interpreted the same.
$VINTAGE, 0
```

2. [R]-[wL] option: set XOPT = FREQ (see point 4) on the miscellaneous data card. (FREQ = value of rated frequency at which tests were performed)

```
$VINTAGE, 1
  USE RL
C punched output cards: L and R read in Ohms, but interpreted in Henries and Ohms
C                        respectively. This explains a factor of about 3.18 E-3 difference
C                        between left and right hand side.
$VINTAGE, 0
```

Use this [R]-[wL] option only if the per unit excitation current is sufficiently large. In case of a near-zero excitation current, the admittance matrix $[A] = [L]^{-1}$ is near -singular and hence cannot be inverted to produce an [L] matrix. The [A]-[R] notation should be used in such case.

At this stage, nonlinearities (such as saturation and hysteresis) can be added to the linear model, as obtained by BCTRAN, whenever necessary. In such case, however, it is mandatory to specify $I_{ex,dir} = 0$, since otherwise the magnetizing inductance will be taken into account twice.

XIX-D. "CHANGE SWITCH" to Convert Former Switched-R,L Elements to Type-99, 98

Section II-A-42 explains the reason for the "CHANGE SWITCH" feature in considerable detail, and that introduction will not be repeated here. Nor will there be any explanation of former switched-R and switched-L element formats, which can be found in Rule Books printed earlier than the 1982 removal of such elements.

Following the "CHANGE SWITCH" request, the user can place an old EMTF data in its entirety, if this is most convenient. What the program does is discard all input cards through the first blank card (for a complete data case, this would be the blank card ending branch cards). Then it reads cards that are assumed to be switch cards, until the blank card terminating these. All later cards, through the following "BEGIN NEW DATA CASE" separator card, are also ignored. So, it is only switch cards that are considered, and only the switched-R and switched-L elements among these are actually processed. Other switches are ignored. This illustrated by the second subcase of BENCHMARK DC-14, which contains informative comment information:

```

BEGIN NEW DATA CASE
C      2nd of 2 subcases converts old Type-91, 92, or 93 to pseudo-nonlinear.
CHANGE SWITCH
  NODE1 NODE2          1.0      ( Series R-L-C will be discarded, of course
91LEFT  RIGHT         0.3E6    ( From p. 20 example of 1980 Rule Book ) 1
      0.0              300.
      0.3              200.
      0.6              150.
     1000.             150.
     9999
91 NODE1 NODE2 COPYL COPYR .25E6 ( Final card from p. 20 of 1980 Rule Book
BLANK card ending program branch cards. This is flag that switches follow.
C      Type-92 switched-R element follows (to be converted):
92JDAYA LMONA         8.5      3.25  3.5E5  3
C      Type-93 switched-L element follows (to be converted):
93SENDA NEUTRL        4.2      2.5   0.7   3.3  1
BLANK card terminating program switch cards
BEGIN NEW DATA CASE
SPUNCH ( Flush the punched-card output of equivalent pseudo-nonlinear elements
BLANK
  
```

Punched output includes the original switch cards on comment cards as documentation for the Type-98 and Type-99 elements that follow. Other comment cards label the new data. This is illustrated by the beginning of the punched output from BENCHMARK DC-14:

<pre> Marker card preceding new EMTF data case. Comment card. NUMDCD = 63. Convert switched-R,L cards to pseudo-nonlinear. This code will read data types 91-Time-Dependent R, 92-Switched Resistance, and 93-Switched Inductor. Such old data will be converted, and punched as pseudo-nonlinear elements to meet modern EMTF requirements. Type-91: piecewise linear resistor Characteristic. 0.0 300. Characteristic. 0.3 200. Characteristic. 0.6 150. Characteristic. 1000. 150. Characteristic. 9999 Type-91: piecewise linear resistor Comment card. NUMDCD = 77. Comment card. NUMDCD = 78. Type-92: switched resistance Comment card. NUMDCD = 80. Type-93: Switched inductance Request for flushing of punch buffer. </pre>	<pre> BEGIN NEW DATA CASE C 2nd of 2 subcases converts old Type-91, 92, or 93 to pseudo-nonlinear. CHANGE SWITCH 91LEFT RIGHT 0.3E6 1 0.0 300. 0.3 200. 0.6 150. 1000. 150. 9999 91 NODE1 NODE2 COPYL COPYR .25E6 C Type-92 switched-R element follows (to be converted): C 0456789012345678901234567890123456789012345678901234567890 92JDAYA LMONA 8.5 3.25 3.5E5 3 C Type-93 switched-L element follows (to be converted): 93SENDA NEUTRL 4.2 2.5 0.7 3.3 1 SPUNCH (Flush the punched-card output of equivalent pseudo-nonlinear elements </pre>
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A listing of 90-column card images now being flushed from punch buffer follows.

 123456789012345678901234567890123456789012345678901234567890123456789

C	91LEFT	RIGHT		0.386	
	91LEFT	RIGHT			3333.
C			VSTART		
			0.386		
C			TR in sec.	R(TR) in ohms	
C			0.0	300.	
			0.0		300.
C			0.3	200.	
			0.3		200.
C			0.6	150.	
			0.6		150.
C			1000.	150.	
			1000.		150.
C			9999		
			9999		

 :
 :
 :
 -----(End of LUNIT7 punched cards as flushed by SPUNCE request)-----